

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DIARRA****FIRST NAME: EMMANUEL****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: not calculated

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2019 on Windows 11)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. US or UK English and their Differences (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
4. Avoiding Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
6. Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 44-57)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2021, 59-64)

GUIDELINES AND IMPORTANT RULES IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic research and writing must follow some rules and guidelines to make a difference from ordinary productions. For his candidates to research and write (masters and doctoral students), EUCLID has developed the ACA-401D Coursepack as guidelines to support them to master the fundamental of those rules and expect high-quality academic papers production from them during their academic journey and onward. The guidelines lead the student through different considerations in terms of writing, punctuation rules, how to stay authentic by avoiding plagiarism, rules of style, and the difference between US and UK English as well as the necessity to avoid using both in the same document. Authenticity and quality writing must be the leading lines in academic research. But from a personal perspective, the distinction between US and UK English in writing applied mainly to students like me with different backgrounds than English. As a French speaker living in a francophone country and having another mother tongue, we have been learning English only for communication and work purposes. The writing component was only for professional production (project proposals or reports). The current paper makes a summary

of what should be my reference for good writing, punctuation, using US or UK English, avoiding plagiarism, style in writing, and rules of Latin abbreviations and expressions and apply them throughout my training program productions such as response papers, major papers and finally on the doctoral thesis.

2) ESSAY WRITING

It is about academic essays. An early start-up is recommended with questions and an initial plan. Based on that, the research on the topic can easily continue and must be oriented about what one already knows or need to know about the topic, the useful material, and the possibility of using it to support the answer to the research questions. The ideas should be organized upon the possible responses to questions and discussions. The findings and ideas will help draft the essay on a standard structure of an introduction, body, and conclusion, considering the rules applied to paragraphs. The essay need to be written clearly. For that it is advised to “make the first step by writing short sentences, avoiding page-long paragraphs, and being careful to signal transitions” (EUCLID 2011, 14). The ready draft will need referencing to prevent plagiarism before editing it for quality improvement. The editing can involve tiers person who can provide criticism to the document. Eventual comments and observations will be addressed before handing in the document to the right person, the right way, and on time. Good time management will allow you to “Put the essay aside for a few days... to consider your essay with a fresh eye” (EUCLID 2021, 11).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

I have been told the story of this prisoner somewhere in a kingdom that the King wanted to set free. Unfortunately, he got executed because of the wrong punctuation in the message that was supposed to be written on the door of his jail cell. Instead of writing “Libérer, pas tuer” (set free, not kill), the comma was moved to give “Libérer pas, tuer” (set free not, kill). Then we understand that wrong punctuation can greatly impact our writing. Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, in the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1 2021, have accentuated the punctuation by giving examples to guide us as students and researchers. The recommended general rule is to “use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence” (EUCLID 2021,16). We learned, for instance the use of apostrophes to indicate possession in different situations of singular or plural nouns or when contracting letters. The ways of using punctuation when dealing with bullet points were also illustrated, as well as the use of colon and semicolon. I could see that the pair comma is used in the same way in French when the description can be removed without altering the sentence. Dashes and hyphens are also covered with examples and in different situations. Other relevant common punctuations are covered, such as ellipsis, full stops, exclamation marks, question marks and quotation marks. Before moving to the next point relative to the difference between US and UK English, we “note(d) that American English has different rules about the use of quotation marks” (EUCLID 2021, 23).

4) US OR UK ENGLISH AND THEIR DIFFERENCES

As explained above, being a French speaker, living in a francophone country, and having another mother tongue, the origin (US or British) did not matter for us when using/speaking English. “American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with “educated” or “scientific” English” (EUCLID 2021, 25). But with this module, I see the necessity of consistency with US or UK English in academic writing. There is no impact on the writer when different pronunciations but the same spelling. But special attention is needed when different spelling but the same pronunciation. Some examples were provided, such as “axe_ax; plough_plow; colour_color; centre_center” (EUCLID 2021, 25). The writer must also pay attention to those words which are the same but have different or additional meanings. Another specific aspect that got my attention personally was the syntax, punctuation, and general usage between US and UK, for instance, when writing honorifics. I used to put a period to honorific abbreviation systematically before learning here that only Dr ends with a period (Dr.) in UK English. As students, we are also invited to avoid jargon, regional variation, or stereotyping in writing. In US or UK English, date writing should also follow a consistent starting with year, month, and day to avoid confusion.

5) PLAGIARISM

“Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34). As a Malian citizen, plagiarism recalls the sad case of Yambo Ouologuem. This Malian author was disgraced because of plagiarism (right or wrong) after publishing “Le Devoir de violence,” Seuil, 1968, despite the success of the book. He did other publications but under a pseudonym before retiring to his native region of Badiangara and died in 2017 in Sevaré in total anonymity. To avoid plagiarism, we must properly cite the author or source of information we use in our writing. For that, there are different ways for in-text citations, paraphrases, or quotations to give exactly what the author has said. I learned also that it is not necessary to cite in some cases, such as when the information is common knowledge. The basic formats to follow were also provided for books, online works, and footnote referencing. “In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using” (EUCLID 2021, 34).

6) STYLE GUIDE

I worked in different organizations and could see that they recommend some specific ways of formatting documents, sometimes emphasizing the police and font to use. I understand now that everything is about style. “A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 41). The indication was clear that EUCLID was fine with other internationally recognized rules but with a preference for Turabian as well as America

English. There is no single authoritative source on style for writing English as well-known and standard rules when it comes to punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary. Nevertheless, “there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 41).

7) CHICAGO STYLE

“Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996” (EUCLID 2021, 44). As explained above, this is the recommended style at EUCLID and should be my style bible as a EUCLID student. Beyond the Style and Usage, it also provides the standard in Page Formatting as well as End/Footnotes. I learned, for instance, that I should begin a sentence with an acronym only if it is the only way to rewrite it. After giving the meaning in the first use, I easily use the acronym with no distinction, whether at the beginning or middle of a sentence. That should be corrected for now. The rules about Ethnic/racial Groups or Geographical Names, among others, were also exposed, including page formatting, end/footnotes, tables, and bibliographies. As far as abbreviations are concerned, they “should be used only in contexts where they are clear to readers” (EUCLID 2021, 44).

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

In French literature, using Latin abbreviations and expressions is so common. Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma gave two interesting tables showing common Latin abbreviations and expressions and their English meaning in the coursepack. Although, they recommended “in business, formal, and technical writing (to) use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation...” with the possibility of using them in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing. “Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (e.g., the information in parentheses)” (EUCLID 2021, 59).

CONCLUSION

The ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1 is an excellent introduction for new students, mainly for those like me with francophone background or who have left classes for a while. The guidelines will help to improve my writing in a progressive way while progressing in the program with the different response papers or master papers until the doctoral thesis. That will make me successful in terms of writing, punctuation rules, and authenticity by avoiding plagiarism and staying consistent with rules of style and language.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University

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